

STRENGTH OF Al₂O₃/Al -ALLOY COMPOSITES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY : The short-term tensile strengths at elevated temperatures were studied for Al₂O₃ short fibers reinforced two aluminum alloys, Al₂O₃/Al-7Si-0.6Mg and Al₂O₃/Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg subjected to various heat treatments. Strengths of the composites decreased with elevated temperatures. However, the strengths were substantially higher than those of the unreinforced matrix alloys. The reasons for the improvement in strength were that the fibers carried on a part of loads, and that the fibers traversing grain boundaries reinforced the grain boundaries and hence resisted their sliding at elevated temperatures. Age-hardening effect was weakened with elevated temperature, especially for Al₂O₃/Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg composite. Therefore, at all test temperatures, there was no great difference in strengths, and strengths decreased very gently with temperatures for the two composites subjected to temper treatment at 300°C for 200 hrs due to eliminating age hardening. After a treatment improved fiber/matrix interface bonding, the composites showed a higher strength than those subjected to age-hardening treatment.

KEYWORDS: Al₂O₃/Al alloy composite, high temperature strength, heat treatment, microstructure, interface bonding, squeeze-casting

INTRODUCTION

One of the aims of reinforcing alloys with fibres is to improve their strengths, especially the strengths at high temperature. In general, metal matrix composites (MMCs) reinforced with continuous ceramic fibres can possess good strength at high temperature, while MMCs reinforced with discontinuous reinforcements possess lower strengths at high temperature. Nevertheless, relative to unreinforced matrix alloys, the high temperature strengths of discontinuous reinforcements MMCs are improved much^(1,2), even their room temperature strengths are not always improved.^(3,4) It is because of not being improved their strengths at ambient temperature that the discontinuous reinforcements MMCs are often subjected to heat treatment to get good mechanical property⁽⁵⁾. Then, can heat treatment improve the high temperature strengths of this kind of MMCs? What are the effects of heat treatment on interfaces between the fibres and matrix, and therefore on the strengths of the composites? Why the short fibres in MMCs can improve the strength of materials at elevated temperature? These are the contains the paper deals with.

MATERIALS AND TESTS

Two Al-alloy composites reinforced with Al_2O_3 short fibers of 20% in volume, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-7Si-0.6Mg}$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg}$ in which the fibers were dispersed randomly, were fabricated by squeeze-casting, and then were applied to the following three different heat treatments:

(1). T_6 treatment

For $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-7Si-0.6Mg}$, solution at 510°C for 6hrs \rightarrow water quenching (70°C) \rightarrow temper at 160°C for 6hrs.

For $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg}$, solution at 540°C for 6hrs \rightarrow water quenching (25°C) \rightarrow temper at 160°C for 6hrs.

(2). T_v treatment

After T_6 treatment, some specimens of two composites were tempered at 300°C for 200 hrs, then quenched into water of 25°C , in order to get a stable material microstructure and stable property at the temperature below 300°C .

(3). T_s treatment

Some specimens of the composites were applied the following treatments in order to improve the fiber/matrix interface bonding.

For $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-7Si-0.6Mg}$, solution at 525°C for 4hrs in vacuum + T_6

For $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg}$, solution at 555°C for 4hrs in vacuum + T_6

After the three treatments, some of specimens were polished, and then examined by scanning electrical microscope and/or optical microscope. After that, tensile tests were performed on the materials at both room temperature and 200, 250, 300 and 350°C , using an Instron 115 material test machine. The specimen design is shown in Fig.1. The specimens polished and examined before tensile tests were again examined by scanning electrical microscope or optical microscope after tensile tests.

Fig.1. Specimen dimensions for tensile test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Like commercial aluminum alloys, the strengths of the two composites decreased with the elevated temperatures, no matter which heat treatment the composites were subjected to, as shown in Fig.2. However, strengths of the composites were substantially higher than those of the unreinforced matrix alloys. One of the reasons for this improvement in strength was that

Fig.2. Strength vs temperature for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-7Si-0.6Mg}$ composite and the matrix alone

the fibers, whose strength can not be degraded at the temperatures below $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, carried on a part of the loads. But the most important reason was that the fibers traversing grain boundaries reinforced the grain boundaries and hence resisted their sliding at elevated temperatures. This can be seen from the metallographical examination in which grain sliding arose in the zones without fiber, not in the zones with fibers as shown in Fig.3. The same phenomenon was observed during creep test on these two composites⁽⁶⁾.

Fig.3. Grain boundary cracked in a zone without fibers during tensile test at $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (1200x)

For the specimens subjected to T₆ treatment, the higher the temperatures were, the closer the strengths of the two composites. They showed almost the same strength at 350 °C, even though their strengths at room temperature were very different (compare Fig.2. with Fig.4.). It indicated that the function of the alloying additions in the matrix decreased with elevated temperatures; in other words, age-hardening effect was weakened especially for Al₂O₃/Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg composite. The examination by scanning electric microscope approved that after a tensile test at 300 °C, some new phases were precipitated in Al₂O₃/Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg composite as presented in Fig.5, but not in Al₂O₃/Al-7Si-0.6Mg composite.

Fig.4. Strength vs temperature for Al₂O₃/Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg composite

Fig.5. New phases (white small dots and line) precipitated in Al₂O₃/Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg composite at 300°C

At all test temperatures, there was no great difference in strength for the two composites subjected to T_v treatment, which can be seen after comparing Fig.2 with Fig.4. T_v treatment

resulted in eliminating age hardening, which was approved by precipitating a lot of small dots containing additions in the matrixes after Tv treatment. It is interesting to notice that the strengths of the two composites subjected to Tv treatment decreased very gently with temperatures (see Fig.2. and Fig.4.). It suggests that most of the decrease in strength with temperature for the composites subjected to T6 treatments should be resulted from eliminating age hardening. Without age hardening, reinforcement effect of the fibers in the composites is significant; and composite strength depends principally on fiber/matrix interface or load transfer capability of the matrix. Therefore, gentle decrease in strength of the composites resulted firstly from the matrix and secondly from some weaker interfaces in the composites. For the same composite respectively subjected to T6 and Ts treatment, it can be seen from Fig.2 and Fig.4 that the specimens subjected to Ts treatments showed a higher strength than those subjected to T6 treatment. Metallographical examination showed that there was more fiber/matrix interface debonding in the fracture surfaces of composite specimens subjected to T6 treatment than in those subjected to Ts treatment as shown in Fig.6. It seems that Ts treatments improved fiber/matrix interface bonding. In fact, during Ts treatment, magnesium in matrix diffused into alumina fibers and reacted with the fibers as indicated in Fig.7.

a. T6 treatment (10000x)

b. Ts treatment (500x)

Fig.6. Two polished fracture surface sides for Al₂O₃/Al-5Si-3Cu-1Mg composite

Fig.7. EDX image of Mg diffused into an alumina fiber

SUMMARY

In conclusion, the reduction in high temperature strength of the composites subjected to T6 treatment attributed mainly to weakening even eliminating age-hardening effect at elevated temperatures; the intrinsic strength of the composites, i.e. the strength without age-hardening effect, varied gently with temperature. It is evident that for MMCs used at high temperature, it is useless to strengthen matrix by age hardening. On the other hand, it is necessary to improve the fiber/matrix bonding by appropriate heat treatment because the strong fibre/matrix interfaces were more important at elevated temperature than at room temperature.

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